

Consiglio Nazionale
delle Ricerche

nextGenIT
Consolidation of the Italian Infrastructure
for Omics Data and Bioinformatics

ELIXIR-IT All Hands Meeting 2023

***"Bringing together
Communities and Platforms"***

November 27th-28th

📍 CNR - Rome, Italy

Italian Proteomics Community

Pierluigi Mauri

Maria Gabriella Giuffrida

Claudia Desiderio

The ELIXIR Proteomics Community was started in 2017

The goal of the ELIXIR Proteomics Community is to develop and maintain sustainable proteomics tools and data resources. An essential part of the development is to allow resources [FAIR](#) - (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable).

Italian Proteomics Community
was started in 2020

- Organization of Events (European Biotech Weeks, ProteomiX)
- Co-founders of Scientific Networks (EPAN, DGNCT, EuroGlycaNet, ProMeTeo, et others)
- IS Proteomics 2019-2021
 2021-2023
- Infrastructures CNR.Biomics
 NextGenElixir
- PNRR Projects
- Clinical Trials, National and International
- Training (Discussion groups, Master – qOmics)
- Partner in the design and implementation of research projects in the field of plant, food, microbial, animal, biology and medicine biology

Integration of Molecular profiles by Systems Biology by High Throughput Technologies

Communities - Connectedness

- Protein-centric communities, IDP & 3DBioinfo
- Analytical platform: Metabolomics
- Omics Integration: Systems Biology

Lifestyle

Biomarker discovery and Molecular mechanisms require a strinhent correlation to Application Communities, mainly:

- Human
- Food & Nutrition
- Plants
- Rare diseases
- Microbiome/Virus

- IS Proteomics 2019-2021
 2021-2023
- PNRR NextGenElixir
- Partner in the design and implementation of research projects in the field of plant, food, microbial, animal, biology and medicine biology
- Clinical Trials, National and International
- Developing Procedures in accordance with regulations
 Privacy and security
- Experimental Data
 - > $2 \cdot 10^4$ Samples/year
 - > $4 \cdot 10^4$ raw files/protein lists/year
 - > 10^{7-8} Identified (redundant) Proteins

Communities citation distribution by service (e.g. MINT Service)

Total Citations: 1379

Communication, Industry and Impact in ELIXIR-IT, by Chiara Bruno, Marilena D'Ambrosio, Francesca De Leo; Contributors: Ivan Mičetić, Federico Zambelli

Since 2021
It has been founded

ProMeTeo

It is the CNR ProTeoMe Network
distributed throughout the national territory

FOCUS

<https://dsb.cnr.it/>

Involving

- 7 Institutes from 3 Departments
- 30 Researchers
- 9 Technicians
- 20 post-doc
- 21 mass spectrometers

Objectives

- carry out scientific projects in collaboration with CNR colleagues, companies, hospitals, universities, and research institutions (national and international).
- act as a partner in the design and implementation of research projects in the field of plant, microbial, animal and medical biology
- train new generations of researchers in the proteomics field, in order to implement the activities of the Network and promoting the development and application of Proteomics

Proteomics Community was involved in the management and teaching in the «**qOmics**» master, coordinated by University of Milano-Bicocca

The master "**qOmics**" is a 2nd level Postgraduate Master Programmes in **applied omics data integration** with a strong focus on quantitative approaches.

The course will be start next April 2024,
Registration from January 2024.

Contact: gomics@unimib.it
<https://qomicsmaster.wordpress.com/>

PROTEOMIX *reloaded...*
"Mix your knowledge to get more!"
Since 2002

Since 2002 **ProteomiX** is an informal meeting on technical problems related to Proteomics.

ProteomiX is an interactive workshop based on open discussion involving young researchers

ELIXIR Italy Proteomics Community Workshop 2023

XXI Edition - ProteomiX - Mix your knowledge to get more!". Discussion group on Proteomics

November 28th - 29th

📍 Sala ex-Biblioteca (Edificio CU027 - 2° piano)
Dipartimento di Scienze Biochimiche "A. Rossi Fanelli", Sapienza Università

XXI Edition – Rome 2023

Allergenomics: Proteomic applications in food allergy

Maria Gabriella Giuffrida ISPA-CNR Turin

- 1998 **Identification of actinidin as the major allergen of kiwi fruit** J ALLERGY CLIN IMMUNOL
- 1999 **Clinical role of a lipid transfer protein that acts as a new apple-specific allergen** J ALLERGY CLIN IMMUNOL
- 2000 **Evidence for a lipid transfer protein as the major allergen of apricot** J ALLERGY CLIN IMMUNOL
- 2000 **The maize major allergen, which is responsible for food-induced allergic reactions, is a lipid transfer protein** J ALLERGY CLIN IMMUNOL
- 2001 The major allergen of sesame seeds (*Sesamum indicum*) is a 2S albumin Journal of Chromatography B.
- 2001 Characterization of the major allergen of plum as a lipid transfer protein
- 2003 **Identification of grape and wine allergens as an endochitinase 4, a lipid-transfer protein, and a thaumatin**
- 2004 **Cow's milk allergens identification by two-dimensional immunoblotting and mass spectrometry**
- 2005 **Novel isoforms of Pru av 1 with diverging immunoglobulin E binding properties identified by a synergistic combination of molecular biology and proteomics**
- ...

In collaboration with allergologists of:

- Children Hospital Regina Margherita of Turin, Italy**
- ✓ **Department of Allergology and Immunology, ASST Grande Ospedale Metropolitano Niguarda, Milan, Italy**
- ✓ **Allergologia e Immunologia Clinica A.O. Ordine Mauriziano Umberto I, University of Turin, Italy**

4 EU projects funded

Cor a 15 is now present in all main database

ALLERGEN NOMENCLATURE

WHO/IUIS Allergen Nomenclature Sub-Committee

Financial contributions from IUIS, EAACI, and AAAAI

Home Search Tree View Publications Carbohydrate Epitopes Sub-Committee Allergen Submission Log In

Plantae Eudicotyledons Fagales *Corvus avellana* Cor a 15

Allergen Details:

Allergen name:	Cor a 15
Allergen source:	Major taxonomic group: Plantae Eudicotyledons Order: Fagales Species: Corvus avellana (Hazelnut)
Biochemical name:	Oleosin
MW(SDS-PAGE):	17 kDa
Allergenicity:	Pediatric food allergic subjects: 17 tested positive for IgE binding out of 26 subjects to natural and recombinant. There were 5 negative controls: IgE binding was with 1D and 2D immunoblots from oilbody extracts. Also 2 µg recombinant protein could inhibit IgE binding. Test subjects: 30 of 30 tested positive by SPT to hazelnut. 18 of 30 subjects were positive by in vivo challenge to whole seed.
Allergenicity reference:	PubMed: 34146442
Route of allergen exposure:	Food
Date Created:	07-07-2019
Last Updated:	2023-07-17 18:17:06
Submitter Info:	
Name:	Maria Gabriella Giuffrida, Giovanna Monti
Institution:	CNR, ISPA; Regina Margherita Children
City:	Grugliasco, Italy, Turin, Italy
Email:	gabriella.giuffrida@ispa.cnr.it , giovanna.monti@email.it
Submission Date:	2019-06-06

NIH National Library of Medicine National Center for Biotechnology Information

Nucleotide

GenBank

Corylus avellana oleosin Cor-a-15 mRNA, complete cds

GenBank: MK737923.1

[FASTA](#) [Graphics](#)

[Go to:](#)

LOCUS MK737923 532 bp mRNA linear PLN 22-JUN-2021
 DEFINITION Corylus avellana oleosin Cor-a-15 mRNA, complete cds.
 ACCESSION MK737923
 VERSION MK737923.1
 KEYWORDS .
 SOURCE Corylus avellana
 ORGANISM Corylus avellana
 Eukaryota; Viridiplantae; Streptophyta; Embryophyta; Tracheophyta;
 Spermatophyta; Magnoliopsida; eudicotyledons; Gunneridae;
 Pentapetalae; rosids; fabids; Fagales; Betulaceae; Corylus.
 REFERENCE 1 (bases 1 to 532)
 AUTHORS Nebbia,S., Lamberti,C., Cirrincione,S., Acquadro,A., Abba,S.,
 Ciuffo,M., Torello Marinoni,D., Manfredi,M., Marengo,E.,
 Calzedda,R., Monti,G., Cavallar,L. and Giuffrida,M.G.
 TITLE Oleosin Cor a 15 is a novel allergen for Italian hazelnut allergic
 children
 JOURNAL [Pediatr Allergy Immunol](#) (2021) In press
 PUBMED [34146442](#)
 REMARK Publication Status: Available-Online prior to print
 REFERENCE 2 (bases 1 to 532)
 AUTHORS Nebbia,S., Lamberti,C., Cirrincione,S., Acquadro,A., Torello
 Marinoni,D., Manfredi,M., Marengo,E., Calzedda,R., Abba,S.,
 Monti,G., Cavallar,L. and Giuffrida,M.G.
 DIRECT SUBMISSION
 JOURNAL Submitted (29-MAR-2019) ISPA, CNR, Largo Braccini 2, Grugliasco,
 Turin 10095, Italia
 COMMENT ##Assembly-Data-START##
 Assembly Method :: Velvet v. 1.2.09
 Assembly Name :: TGL-1.0
 Coverage :: 60X
 Sequencing Technology :: Illumina
 ##Assembly-Data-END##

NIH National Library of Medicine National Center for Biotechnology Information

Protein

GenPept

RecName: Full=Oleosin Cor a 15; AltName: Allergen=Cor a 15

UniProtKB/Swiss-Prot: C0HM28.1

[Identical Proteins](#) [FASTA](#) [Graphics](#)

[Go to:](#)

LOCUS OLE15_CORAV 169 aa linear PLN 03-MAY-2023
 DEFINITION RecName: Full=Oleosin Cor a 15; AltName: Allergen=Cor a 15.
 ACCESSION C0HM28
 VERSION C0HM28.1
 DBSOURCE UniProtKB: locus OLE15_CORAV, accession [C0HM28](#);
 class: standard.
 created: Aug 3, 2022.
 sequence updated: Aug 3, 2022.
 annotation updated: May 3, 2023.
 xrefs: MK737923.1, QEH21451.1
 xrefs (non-sequence databases): GO:0016020, GO:0012511, GO:0009791,
 GO:0048608, InterPro:IPR000136, PANTHER:PTHR33203,
 PANTHER:PTHR33203:SF44, Pfam:PF01277
 KEYWORDS Allergen; Direct protein sequencing; Lipid droplet; Membrane;
 Transmembrane; Transmembrane helix.
 SOURCE Corylus avellana
 ORGANISM Corylus avellana
 Eukaryota; Viridiplantae; Streptophyta; Embryophyta; Tracheophyta;
 Spermatophyta; Magnoliopsida; eudicotyledons; Gunneridae;
 Pentapetalae; rosids; fabids; Fagales; Betulaceae; Corylus.
 REFERENCE 1 (residues 1 to 169)
 AUTHORS Nebbia,S., Lamberti,C., Cirrincione,S., Acquadro,A., Abba,S.,
 Ciuffo,M., Torello Marinoni,D., Manfredi,M., Marengo,E.,
 Calzedda,R., Monti,G., Cavallar,L. and Giuffrida,M.G.
 TITLE Oleosin Cor a 15 is a novel allergen for Italian hazelnut allergic
 children
 JOURNAL [Pediatr Allergy Immunol](#) 32 (8), 1743-1755 (2021)
 PUBMED [34146442](#)
 REMARK NUCLEOTIDE SEQUENCE [MRNA], PROTEIN SEQUENCE OF 2-12, FUNCTION,
 TISSUE SPECIFICITY, MASS SPECTROMETRY, AND ALLERGEN.

UniProt BLAST Align Peptide search ID mapping SPARQL UniProtKB

|Function

C0HM28 · OLE15_CORAV

Names & Taxonomy

Protein¹ | Oleosin Cor a 15

Amino acids | 169 [\(go to sequence\)](#)

Subcellular Location

Status¹ | UniProtKB reviewed (Swiss-Prot)

Protein existence¹ | Evidence at protein level

Phenotypes & Variants

Organism¹ | [Corylus avellana \(European hazel\)](#) ([Corylus maxima](#))

Annotation score¹ | [35](#)

PTM/Processing

[Entry](#)

[Variant viewer](#)

[Feature viewer](#)

[Genomic coordinates](#)

[Publications](#)

[External links](#)

[History](#)

Food allergies to cross-reactive carbohydrate determinants (CCD):

Alpha-gal syndrome

Alpha-gal syndrome (AGS) is a **mammalian meat delayed allergy** associated with tick bites and specific IgE antibodies to the oligosaccharide galactose- α -1,3-galactose (α -gal). Several recent studies demonstrated that **proteins but also fat fraction of bovine milk** might contain α -Gal-epitopes.

Milk Fat Globule Membrane (MFGM) Proteins of bovine milk

- Xanthine Oxidase (XO)
- Xanthine Oxidase (XO)
- Butyrophillin (BT)
- Butyrophillin (BT)
- Lactoadherine (LA)

LDS page and immunoblotting of MFGP, MFGP after anti- α -gal IgG/beads incubation (MFGPb) and MFGPb deglycosilated.

Available online at www.sciencedirect.com
 ScienceDirect
 Biochimica et Biophysica Acta 1780 (2008) 75–88
 ELSEVIER
 BBA
www.elsevier.com/locate/bbagen

Review

The Gal α 1,3Gal β 1,4GlcNAc-R (α -Gal) epitope: A carbohydrate of unique evolution and clinical relevance

Curr Allergy Asthma Rep (2013) 13:72–77
 DOI 10.1007/s11882-012-0315-y

ANAPHYLAXIS AND DRUG ALLERGY (P. LIEBERMAN AND S. SPECTOR, SECTION EDITORS)

ZENTRUM FÜR PATHOPHYSIOLOGIE, INFEKTILOGIE UND IMMUNOLOGIE
 MEDIZINISCHE UNIVERSITÄT WIEN

Collaboration with the group of Prof. Karin Hoffmann-Sommergruber

Delayed Anaphylaxis to Red Meat in Patients with IgE Specific for Galactose alpha-1,3-Galactose (alpha-gal)

Scott P. Commins · Thomas A. E. Platts-Mills

IN VIVO TESTING TO CONFIRM ALLERGENICITY

Basophil Activation Test (BAT)

Food safety and innovative methods for food analysis

Development of analytical method for detection and quantification of melamine in milk and cookies

Method able to detect and quantify melamine as low as 1.3 mg milk/kg cookies

Food Chemistry 199 (2016) 119–127

Contents lists available at ScienceDirect

Food Chemistry

journal homepage: www.elsevier.com/locate/foodchem

Analytical Methods

Validation of a mass spectrometry-based method for milk traces detection in baked food

Lamberti Cristina^a, Acquadro Elena^b, Corpillo Davide^b, Giribaldi Marzia^a, Decastelli Lucia^c, Garino Cristiano^d, Arlorio Marco^d, Ricciardi Carlo^e, Cavallarini Laura^a, Giuffrida Maria Gabriella^{a,*}

Multi-target detection of egg-white and pig gelatin fining agents in Nebbiolo-based aged red wine by means of nanoHPLC-HRMS

Federica Dal Bello^a, Cristina Lamberti^{b,*}, Marzia Giribaldi^c, Cristiano Garino^{d,1}, Monica Locatelli^d, Daniela Gastaldi^a, Claudio Medana^a, Laura Cavallarini^b, Marco Arlorio^d, Maria Gabriella Giuffrida^b

^a Department of Molecular Biotechnology and Health Sciences, University of Turin, via Pietro Giuria 5, 10125 Torino, Italy
^b Institute of Sciences of Food Production, National Research Council, Largo Braconni 2, 10095 Grugliasco (TO), Italy
^c CREA Research Centre for Engineering and Agro-Food Processing, Strada delle Case 73, 10135 Torino, Italy
^d Dipartimento di Scienze del Farmaco, Università del Piemonte Orientale "Amedeo Avogadro", Largo Donegani 2, 28100 Novara, Italy

Now we are developing a **metrologically traceable MS-based reference procedures for protein allergen quantification in red wine**

Fundamental protein metrology to support the definition of measurands, analytical targets, and their associated measurement uncertainty (ProMET)

Since 2021 we are partner of **MPreSA**
www.infrastrutturaimpresa.it Metrological Infrastructure for Food Safety

Proteomics of Novel Foods

microalgae

jellyfish

insects

seaweed

Circular and Inclusive utilisation of alternative PROteins in the MEDiterranean value chains

The PRIMA programme is an Art. 185 initiative supported and founded under Horizon 2020, the European Union's Framework Programme for Research and Innovation.

Cross-allergenicity

Contents lists available at ScienceDirect

Food Research International

journal homepage: www.elsevier.com/locate/foodres

Thermal processing of insect allergens and IgE cross-recognition in Italian patients allergic to shrimp, house dust mite and mealworm

Cristina Lamberti^a, Stefano Nebbia^a, Simona Cirrincione^a, Luisa Brussino^{b,*}, Veronica Giorgis^b, Alessandra Romito^c, Cristiana Marchese^c, Marcello Manfredi^d, Emilio Marengo^d, Maria Gabriella Giuffrida^a, Giovanni Rolla^b, Laura Cavallarin^a

INSECT BREEDING

Occupational allergies

Received: 2 May 2019 | Revised: 21 June 2019 | Accepted: 5 July 2019
DOI: 10.1111/ona.13461

RESEARCH LETTER

WILEY

The cockroach allergen-like protein is involved in primary respiratory and food allergy to yellow mealworm (*Tenebrio molitor*)

Clinical Proteomics for Precision Medicine

Claudia Desiderio – Senior Researcher

Istituto di Scienze e Tecnologie
Chimiche (SCITEC) «Giulio Natta»

CNR | Dipartimento Scienze Chimiche
e Tecnologie dei Materiali

Locations:
Milano (headquarter)
Genova
Perugia
Roma

**CHEMISTRY FOR LIFE
SCIENCES**

UNIVERSITÀ CATTOLICA del Sacro Cuore

Catholic University of Sacred Heart
Medicine and Surgery Faculty

Fondazione Policlinico Universitario A. Gemelli IRCCS

Gemelli
Fondazione Policlinico Universitario Agostino Gemelli IRCCS
Università Cattolica del Sacro Cuore

**Clinical Proteomic
investigation**

Clinical Proteomics for Precision Medicine

PEDIATRIC BRAIN TUMORS

- **POSTERIOR FOSSA TUMORS**
MEDULLOBLASTOMA, EPENDIMOMA,
PILOCYTIC ASTROCYTOMA
- **GLIOBLASTOMA**
- **ADAMANTINOMATOUS
CRANIOPHARYNGIOMA**

specimens

- INTRACYSTIC FLUIDS
 - CEREBROSPINAL FLUID
 - TUMOR TISSUES
- TOP-DOWN/BOTTOM-UP
Integrated platforms**

References...

Hindawi
Disease Markers
Volume 2019, Article ID 3609789, 18 pages
<https://doi.org/10.1155/2019/3609789>

Tumor tissue

Research Article

Investigating the Protein Signature of Adamantinomatous Craniopharyngioma Pediatric Brain Tumor Tissue: Towards the Comprehension of Its Aggressive Behavior

Claudia Martelli,¹ Riccardo Serra,² Ilaria Inserra,¹ Diana Valeria Rossetti,^{1,3}
Federica Iavarone,^{1,3} Federica Vincenzoni,^{1,3} Massimo Castagnola,^{4,5} Andrea Urbani,^{1,6}
Gianpiero Tamburrini,^{2,7} Massimo Caldarelli,^{2,7} Luca Massimi,^{2,7} and Claudia Desiderio⁸

Intracystic fluid
Proteomic Study of Pilocytic Astrocytoma Pediatric Brain Tumor Intracystic Fluid

Ilaria Inserra,^{1,8} Federica Iavarone,^{1,8} Claudia Martelli,¹ Luca D'Angelo,^{1,2} Daniela Delfino,¹
Diana Valeria Rossetti,¹ Gianpiero Tamburrini,² Luca Massimi,² Massimo Caldarelli,²
Concezio Di Rocco,³ Irene Messina,³ Massimo Castagnola,⁴ and Claudia Desiderio⁸⁻¹

MINI-SYMPOSIUM: Adamantinomatous Craniopharyngioma and Xanthomatous Lesions of the Sella

Proteomics in pediatric cystic craniopharyngioma

Luca Massimi¹, Claudia Martelli², Massimo Caldarelli¹, Massimo Castagnola^{2,3}, Claudia Desiderio³

Molecular
BioSystems

Tumor tissue

PAPER

CrossMark

Cite this: Mol. Biosyst., 2015, 11, 2168

Integrated proteomic platforms for the comparative characterization of medulloblastoma and pilocytic astrocytoma pediatric brain tumors: a preliminary study†

Claudia Martelli,² Federica Iavarone,² Luca D'Angelo,¹ Federica Vincenzoni,¹ Ilaria Inserra,¹ Daniela Delfino,¹ Marta Caretto,² Luca Massimi,² Gianpiero Tamburrini,² Massimo Caldarelli,² Irene Messina,² Massimo Castagnola,³ and Claudia Desiderio^{3*}

2172
Claudia Martelli^{1*}
Federica Iavarone^{1*}
Federica Vincenzoni¹
Diana Valeria Rossetti¹
Luca D'Angelo^{1,2}
Gianpiero Tamburrini²
Massimo Caldarelli²
Concezio Di Rocco³
Irene Messina³
Massimo Castagnola^{1,4}
Claudia Desiderio⁴

Intracystic fluid

Research Article

Proteomic characterization of pediatric craniopharyngioma intracystic fluid by LC-MS top-down/bottom-up integrated approaches

The combination of top-down and bottom-up platforms was utilized for the LC-MS pro-

cancers Tumor tissue

Article

Ependymoma Pediatric Brain Tumor Protein Fingerprinting by Integrated Mass Spectrometry Platforms: A Pilot Investigation

Diana Valeria Rossetti^{1,2,*}, Luca Massimi^{3,4}, Claudia Martelli¹, Federica Vincenzoni^{1,2}, Susanna Di Silvestre³, Gianluca Scorpio³, Gianpiero Tamburrini³, Massimo Caldarelli³, Andrea Urbani^{1,4,*} and Claudia Desiderio^{5,*}

Clinical Proteomics for Precision Medicine

PEDIATRIC BRAIN TUMORS

profiling **PROTEOFORMS** and **PTMs** in tumor tissues of different WHO grade

Article Pediatric Brain Tumors: Signatures from the Intact Proteome

Diana Valeria Rossetti ^{1,2,3}, Iliaria Insera ^{1,4}, Alessia Nesticò ^{4,5}, Federica Vincenzoni ^{1,2,6}, Federica Iavarone ^{1,2}, Irene Messina ^{3,6}, Massimo Castagnola ^{5,6}, Luca Massimi ⁶, Gianpiero Tamburrini ⁶, Massimo Caldarelli ⁶ and Claudia Desiderio ^{3,*}

PROTEOFORMS

Review Citrullination Post-Translational Modification: State of the Art of Brain Tumor Investigations and Future Perspectives

Diana Valeria Rossetti ^{1,4}, Alexandra Muntiu ^{2,4}, Luca Massimi ³, Gianpiero Tamburrini ³ and Claudia Desiderio ^{1,*}

Clinical Proteomics for Precision Medicine

MS-PROTEOMICS: analytical approach

❖ **BOTTOM-UP** approach
(digested proteins analysis)

❖ **TOP-DOWN** approach
(intact proteins/peptides analysis)

International Journal of Molecular Sciences

Review
The Post-Translational Modifications of Human Salivary Peptides and Proteins Evidenced by Top-Down Platforms

Irene Messana¹, Barbara Manconi², Tiziana Cabras^{2*}, Moshgan Boroumand³, Maria Teresa Sanna², Federica Iavarone^{4,5}, Alessandra Ollanas², Claudia Desiderio¹, Diana Valeria Rossetti¹, Federica Vincenzoni^{4,5}, Cristina Contini², Giulia Guadalupi², Antonella Fiorita^{5,6}, Gavino Faa^{7,8} and Massimo Castagnola⁹

CRITICAL REVIEWS IN BIOCHEMISTRY AND MOLECULAR BIOLOGY
2018, VOL. 53, NO. 3, 266-303
<https://doi.org/10.1080/10409238.2018.1447543>

REVIEW ARTICLE

Cryptides: latent peptides everywhere

Federica Iavarone^a, Claudia Desiderio^b, Alberto Vitali^b, Irene Messana^b, Claudia Martelli^c, Massimo Castagnola^{d,e} and Tiziana Cabras^c

^aIstituto di Biochimica e Biochimica Clinica, Università Cattolica, Roma, Italy; ^bIstituto di Chimica del Riconoscimento Molecolare, CNR, Roma, Italy; ^cDipartimento di Scienze della Vita e dell'Ambiente, Università di Cagliari, Cagliari, Italy

High Resolution
MS

MS,
MS² or MSⁿ
fragmentation

- molecular weight (Mw)
- Amino acid sequence
- Isoforms identification
- PTMs identification and localization :
phosphorylation, methylation, acetylation, sulfation,
cystinylation, glutathionylation, N- and C-terminal
modifications

Clinical Proteomics for Precision Medicine

HEMOGLOBIN CRYPTIDES

2158 DOI 10.1002/jmcs.201100499 Proteomics 2012, 12, 2158-2166

RESEARCH ARTICLE

Cerebrospinal fluid top-down proteomics evidenced the potential biomarker role of LVV- and VV-hemorphin-7 in posterior cranial fossa pediatric brain tumors

Claudia Desiderio¹, Luca D'Angelo^{2,3}, Diana Valeria Rossetti², Federica Iavarone², Bruno Giardina^{1,2}, Massimo Castagnola^{1,2}, Luca Massim², Gianpiero Tamburrini³ and Concezio Di Rocco³

¹Istituto di Chimica del Riconoscimento Molecolare, Consiglio Nazionale delle Ricerche, Rome, Italy
²Istituto di Biochimica e Biochimica Clinica, Facoltà di Medicina, Università Cattolica del Sacro Cuore, Rome, Italy
³Reparto di Neurochirurgia Infantile, Istituto di Neurochirurgia - Policlinico Universitario A. Gemelli, Rome, Italy

Journal of Chromatography A, 1267 (2012) 170–177

Development and validation of a capillary electrophoresis tandem mass spectrometry analytical method for the determination of Leu-Val-Val- and Val-Val-hemorphin-7 peptides in cerebrospinal fluid

Mariangela Zeccola⁴, Renato Longhi⁵, Diana Valeria Rossetti¹, Luca D'Angelo^{1,6}, Gianpiero Tamburrini⁶, Concezio Di Rocco⁶, Bruno Giardina^{4,6}, Massimo Castagnola^{4,6}, Claudia Desiderio^{4,6}

⁴Istituto di Chimica del Riconoscimento Molecolare, Consiglio Nazionale delle Ricerche, via Institute di Biochimica e Biochimica Clinica, Università Cattolica del Sacro Cuore, L.go F. Testi 1, 00188 Roma, Italy
⁵Istituto di Chimica del Riconoscimento Molecolare, Consiglio Nazionale delle Ricerche, Via Mario Bianco 5, 00133 Milano, Italy
⁶Istituto di Biochimica e Biochimica Clinica, Università Cattolica del Sacro Cuore, L.go F. Testi 1, 00188 Roma, Italy
⁷Reparto di Neurochirurgia Infantile, Istituto di Neurochirurgia - Policlinico Universitario A. Gemelli, Rome, Italy

PEPTIDE average mass	CSF														Ctrl																		
	PRE							POST							I	II	III	IV	V														
Patient	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14	I	II	III	IV	V
1194.3	X														X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X
1308.4	X														X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X

Subtotal metastasis resection

HEMORPHINS Biological activities

- Non-classical opioid peptides
- ACE inhibitors
- At4 receptor ligand
- β -endorphin connection
- Interaction with bombesin receptor
- homeostasis maintenance

Clinical Proteomics for Precision Medicine

ADULT BRAIN TUMORS GLIOBLASTOMA MULTIFORME

THE PROJECT...

References...

Article

Glioblastoma CUSA Fluid Protein Profiling: A Comparative Investigation of the Core and Peripheral Tumor Zones

Giuseppe La Rocca ^{1,†}, Giorgia Antonia Simboli ^{2,†}, Federica Vincenzoni ^{3,4,†}, Diana Valeria Rossetti ^{3,4}, Andrea Urbani ^{3,4}, Tamara Ius ⁵, Giuseppe Maria Della Pepa ², Alessandro Olivi ², Giovanni Sabatino ^{1,*,†} and Claudia Desiderio ^{6,*,†}

Article

Investigating Glioblastoma Multiforme Sub-Proteomes: A Computational Study of CUSA Fluid Proteomic Data

Fabiana Moresi ^{1,2}, Diana Valeria Rossetti ³, Federica Vincenzoni ^{2,4,†}, Giorgia Antonia Simboli ^{4,5,†}, Giuseppe La Rocca ^{1,4,5}, Alessandro Olivi ^{4,5}, Andrea Urbani ^{2,4}, Giovanni Sabatino ^{1,4,5,†} and Claudia Desiderio ^{3,*,†}

Clinical Proteomics for Regenerative Medicine

Project PRIN (MUR) Bando 2017 - Prot. 2017RSAFK7:

Immunomodulatory properties of the Amniotic Stromal cell Secretome: from Multi-omics profiling to nanotechnology-aided delivery for controlled release in osteoarthritis [ASSEMBLe]

RU1
UNIVERSITÀ CATTOLICA
POLIAMBULANZA
CENTRO DI RICERCA E. MENNI

RU2
UNIVERSITÀ DEGLI STUDI DI PALERMO

RU3
Consiglio Nazionale delle Ricerche
SCITEC

RU4
SAPIENZA
UNIVERSITÀ DI ROMA

RU5
Università degli Studi
Cagliari

RU6
Ud'A
Università del Sud Sardegna

WP3. MULTI-OMICS CHARACTERIZATION OF THE WHOLE SECRETOME AND ITS FRACTIONS
Leaders **RU3**, **RU5**
T3.1 Proteomic profiling and protein fingerprinting [**RU3**] (mo6-24) following both the top-down and the bottom-up approaches.

- whole secretome
- Extracellular Vesicles fraction

Dipt. di Scienze della vita e sanità pubblica, Facoltà di Medicina e Chirurgia, Università Cattolica del Sacro Cuore, Roma.
Project PI

Contract Research
Scientist : Dr A. Muntiu

- Advance the knowledge of the molecular complexity underlying the immunomodulatory properties
- Developing hydrogel based - system of delivery for clinical applications in Osteoarthritis

Muntiu et al. Stem Cell Research & Therapy
<https://doi.org/10.1186/s13287-023-03537-4>

Stem Cell Research & Therapy

RESEARCH Open Access

1 Disclosing the molecular profile
2 of the human amniotic mesenchymal
3 stromal cell secretome by filter-aided sample
4 preparation proteomic characterization
5

6 Alexandra Muntiu^{1†}, Andrea Papai^{2,3†}, Federica Vincenzoni^{1,4}, Alberto Vitali¹, Wanda Lettieri^{1,3}, Pietro Romele⁵,
7 Anna Carignoni⁵, Antonietta Sili⁶, Omella Pardini^{2,3†} and Claudia Desiderio^{1†}

Glycomics and Glycoproteomics

Congenital disorders of glycosylation (CDG)

Rare genetic disorders

that affect the addition of sugar building blocks, glycans, to proteins in cells throughout the body.

EUROGLYCANET: a European network focused on congenital disorders of glycosylation

European Journal of Human Genetics (2005) 13, 395–397

A European research network directed towards improving diagnosis and treatment of inborn errors of glycosylation

EUROGLYCAN-omics

Glycomics and Glycoproteomics

- CDG
- ✓ **170** serum samples from CDG patients
 - ✓ **82** patients identified with N-glycosylation or mixed N-, and O-glycosylation defects

5 new CDG defects discovered:

- DPM2-CDG,
- MAN1B1-CDG,
- SLC35A3-CDG,
- STT3A-CDG,
- CALMG-CDG

212

Y. Ikeda et al.

Fig. 19.1 A reaction catalyzed by GnT-III. A GlcNAc residue linked to an $\alpha\text{1,6Man}$ may be substituted by a Man, and the presence of $\alpha\text{1,6fucosyl}$ residue at the innermost GlcNAc does not affect the action of GnT-III. An acceptor oligosaccharide is active even when its reducing end is modified by reductive amination, e.g., labeling with 2-aminopyridine

Glycomics and Glycoproteomics (CDG)

An aberrant sugar modification of BACE1 blocks its lysosomal targeting in Alzheimer's disease

Lack of bisecting GlcNAc relocates BACE1 from early endosomes (Aβ generation site) to lysosomes, leading to a reduction in both Aβ generation and the level of BACE1 protein.

EMBO Molecular Medicine

Apoptosis induction with high level of Cer is in agreement with proteomics data resulting in an apoptotic pathway enrichment in ARSACS patients

Alteration in DG pathway means deregulation of Ca²⁺ omeostasis highlighted by proteomics

Proteomics and lipidomics analysis reveal lipid and calcium signalling as dysregulated pathways associated to **sacsin (SACS)** loss

Mutations in *SACS* cause Autosomal Recessive Spastic Ataxia of Charlevoix-Saguenay (**ARSACS**), a rare, early-onset inherited neurological disorder

Drug repurposing and combination in breast cancer (TNBC)

MDA-MB-231 cell

Figure 1

Proteomics by DIA approach

Proteomics & Immunology-Cancer

Zoledronic acid boosts $\gamma\delta$ T-cell activity in children receiving $\alpha\beta^+$ T and CD19⁺ cell-depleted grafts from an HLA-haplo-identical donor

A. Bertaina^{a,*}, A. Zorzoli^{b,*}, A. Petretto^{c,*}, G. Barbarito^b, E. Inglese^c, P. Merli^a, C. Lavarello^c, L. P. Brescia^a, B. De Angelis ^a, G. Tripodi^d, L. Moretta^e, F. Locatelli^{a,f,#}, and I. Airoidi^{b,#}

ABSTRACT

We demonstrated that $\gamma\delta$ T cells of patients given HLA-haploidentical HSCT after removal of $\alpha\beta^+$ T cells and CD19⁺ B cells are endowed with the capacity of killing leukemia cells after *ex vivo* treatment with zoledronic acid (ZOL). Thus, we tested the hypothesis that infusion of ZOL in patients receiving this type of

treatment. Proteomic analysis of $\gamma\delta$ T cells purified from patients showed upregulation of proteins involved in activation processes and immune response, paralleled by downregulation of proteins involved in proliferation. Moreover, a proteomic signature was identified for each ZOL treatment. Patients given three or more ZOL infusions had a better probability of survival in comparison to those given one or two treatments (86% vs. 54%, respectively, $p = 0.008$). Our data indicate that ZOL infusion in pediatric recipients of $\alpha\beta$ T- and B-cell-depleted HLA-haploidentical HSCT promotes $\gamma\delta$ T-cell differentiation and cytotoxicity and may influence the outcome of patients.

Proteomics & Lymphocytes

The Proteomic Landscape of Human Ex Vivo Regulatory and Conventional T Cells Reveals Specific Metabolic Requirements

Procaccini et al., *Immunity*, 2016

Cell Metabolism

Caloric Restriction Promotes Immunometabolic Reprogramming Leading to Protection from Tuberculosis

2021

2023

Immune system: discovered a new regulatory mechanism in diseases such as leukemia

This Research has highlighted that the mechanical function of titin plays a role in lymphocyte resilience to passive deformation and mechanical stress

Graphical abstract

Cell Reports

An isoform of the giant protein titin is a master regulator of human T lymphocyte trafficking

Highlights

- Human T and B lymphocytes express five isoforms of the giant protein TTN
- In T lymphocytes, the LTTN1 isoform regulates the structure of microvilli
- LTTN1 regulates integrin activation and chemotaxis
- LTTN1 controls cell stiffness and deformability and ensures survival in the circulation

MCP PERSPECTIVE

Data Management of Sensitive Human Proteomics Data: Current Practices, Recommendations, and Perspectives for the Future

2021

Nuno Bandeira^{1,2,3}, Eric W. Deutsch⁴, Oliver Kohlbacher^{5,6,7,8}, Lennart Martens^{9,10}, and Juan Antonio Vizcaino^{11,*}

Chatterjee et al. BMC Genomics (2016) 17:642
DOI 10.1186/s12864-016-2855-3

BMC Genomics

METHODOLOGY ARTICLE

Open Access

A comprehensive and scalable database search system for metaproteomics

Sandip Chatterjee^{1†}, Gregory S. Stupp^{1†}, Sung Kyu Robin Park^{2†}, Jean-Christophe Ducom³, John R. Yates III², Andrew I. Su^{1,4*} and Dennis W. Wolan^{1,2*}

Italian Experimental Data Production*

- > $2 \cdot 10^4$ Samples/year
 - > $4 \cdot 10^4$ raw files-proteins/year
 - > 10^{7-8} Identified Proteins
- *underestimated

Translational Research Discovery of **biomarkers** useful for **diagnosis**, phenotyping and **therapy** monitoring

NextGenIT

CNR.BiOmics

Fundamental Research
mechanisms (endotypes)
therapies

Elucidation of **molecular**
related to diseases and its

Proteomics Implementation Study 2021

WOMBAT-P: Benchmarking Label-Free Proteomics Data Analysis Workflows

[Accepted 16-Nov-2023](#) - by
Journal of Proteome Research

ID: pr-2023-00636h.R1

Figure 1: Scheme of the WOMBAT-P analysis workflows. They allow different types of input files for setting the workflow parameters and the experimental design.

- ❖ Cytoscape
- ❖ Byonic
- ❖ ClinProtTools
- ❖ Q-GIS

Home-made tools

- ❖ MAProMA
- ❖ Proteome Recovery
- ❖ Alpha-value
- ❖ Others

- ❖ Peaks
- ❖ Protein Pilot
- ❖ ProteinDeconvolution
- ❖ ProteinScape
- ❖ MaxQuant
- ❖ Proteome Discoverer
- ❖ DIA-NN

DIA-NN

R Studio

Important aspects for improving productivity and interactions of Proteomics can be advantaged from **empowerment**

CNR.BiOmics

NextGenIT

ICT platform with high computing power and storage (10K core, 15 Pb storage, and more)

- OR5 Biorepository of Omics data
- OR3 Implementation Computational Platform

- To develop a **repository**, for raw and/or out files
Availability of results for translational and research groups, including Elixir communities
- To improve **friendly interfaces**, for automation of home-made algorithms or procedures, and managing the huge amount of produced data, using AI also.

to Italian Proteomics Community Members

